

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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KURASHCHIDA JISMONIY SIFATLAR

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Anatatsiya: Dunyodagi eng ommabop sport turlaridan biri sifatida kurashni keng omma katta qiziqish bilan kuzatib boradi. Kurashda deyarli har bir yosh toifasidagi insonlar turli maqsadlarda qatnashadilar. Nima maqsadda bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar, kurashchilar kurashning mavjudligi uchun yagona elementdir. So'ngi Alimpiada o'yinlaridan keyin kurashga bo'lgan qiziqish yanada ortdi.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy, morfologik, psixofiziologik, jismoniy imkoniyatlar, kuch, chidamlilik, moslashuvchanlik, chaqqonlik, tezlik, jismoniy fazilatlar, umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlik, funktsional imkoniyatlar, jismoniy kapabil va "jismoniy (motorli) qobiliyatlar".

Kirish

Mavhum. Ushbu maqola umumiy va maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlikni (fazilatlarini) rivojlantirish orqali kurashchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini yaxshilash va kurashchilarning funktsional imkoniyatlarini oshirishga qaratilgan. Kurashchining jismoniy tayyorgarligi sport mashg'ulotlarining muhim tarkibiy qismlaridan biridir. Jismoniy tarbiya jismoniy fazilatlar, kuch, chidamlilik, moslashuvchanlik, chaqqonlik va tezlikni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Jismoniy tarbiya umumiy, yordamchi va maxsus tayyorgarlikka bo'linadi. Kurashchining umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarligi yuqori darajaga chiqish uchun asos, bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Asos quyidagi vazifalarni hal qilishni ta'minlaydi. Tananing har tomonlama rivojlanishi, uning funktsional imkoniyatlarini oshirish va jismoniy imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish haqida ma'lumot kurashga beriladi.

Biroq, ular bir xil emas. Umuman olganda, vosita mahoratini insonning vosita qobiliyatlari darajasini belgilaydigan individual xususiyatlar deb tushunish mumkin. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi: muvozanatni saqlash - bir oyog'ida, uni beqaror qo'llab-quvvatlash, turli aylanishlarni amalga oshirgandan keyin va hokazo. Noyob jangovar mahoratni rivojlantirishning asosiy jihati yangi texnik harakatlarni o'rganish va o'zlashtirish, shuningdek, allaqachon ma'lum bo'lgan texnika va kombinatsiyalarni amalga oshirishdir. Umumiy jismoniy tarbiya turli xil vositalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

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Ularga jihozlarsiz va jihozlar bilan bajariladigan mashqlar, sherik bilan maxsus mashg'ulotlarda bajariladigan mashqlar, boshqa sport turlaridan olingan umumiy rivojlanish mashqlari: akrobatika, yengil atletika, suzish va boshqalar kiradi.

Yordamchi jismoniy tarbiya maxsus asos yaratishga mo'ljallangan maxsus harakat ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan katta hajmdagi ishlarni samarali bajarish uchun zarurdir.

Quyidagi vazifalarni ma'lum bir yo'nalish bilan hal qiladi:

- kurash uchun o'ziga xos fazilatlarni rivojlantirish;

- Kurashchining harakatlarida ishtirok etadigan mushak guruhlarining selektiv rivojlanishi.

Yordamchi jismoniy tarbiyaning ilg'or vositalari sifatida bunday mashqlar qo'llaniladi, ularning kinematik va dinamik tartibiga va nerv-mushak tarangligining xususiyatlariga ko'ra, kurashchining musobaqa davomida bajargan asosiy harakatlariga mos keladi. Bunday mashqlar orasida quyidagilarni ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin: turli xil kurash usullarini ishora qilish orqali bajarish; maxsus o'quv qurilmalarida mashqlarni bajarish.

Adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish va metodologiyasi. Kurashchining maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligi kurashchilarning harakat sifatlarini tomonidan qo'yilgan talablarga qat'iy muvofiq ravishda rivojlantirishga qaratilgan dinamik va statik harakat bo'lib hisoblanadi. Musobaqa davomida mushaklarning juda qisqa vaqt ichida maksimal kuch ko'rsatish qobiliyati alohida ahamiyatga ega va bu kurashchiga musobaqadagi raqibidan ustunlik beradi. Mashhur kurashchilar nafaqat jismoniy tayyorgarlikning yuqori darajada rivojlanishi va texnik usullarning boyligiga ega, balki o'z vaqtida katta kuch ko'rsatish qobiliyati bilan ham ajralib turadi. Ko'plab tadqiqotchilarning natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, mushak massasini sezilarli darajada oshirmasdan kuchni rivojlantirish mumkin: - mushak massasini ko'paytirmasdan kuchni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan mashg'ulotlarda iloji boricha kamroq takrorlash (1-3 marta) katta yuk bilan va harakatlar orasidagi dam olish oraliq'ini oshirish bilan ishlash kerak; - mushak massasini olishda kuchni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan mashqlarda og'irlikni oshirish bilan ishlash kerak.

- Kurashchi ko'targan yukning 50% 8-10 marta takrorlanadi.

Tahlil natijalari. Kurashchining tezligi deganda, u qisqa vaqt ichida muayyan harakatlarni bajarishga qodirligini tushunamiz va kurashchining reaksiyasi yaxshi deganda, u qo'lga olish yoki harakatlarni tez va qisqa vaqt ichida bajarishini

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tushunamiz.vaqtda, himoya qiladi va qarshi choralarini qo'llaydi. Vaziyatga qarab tezkor qarorlar qabul qilish, tezkor harakat reaksiyasini o'rgatish paytida raqib hujumiga qarshi harakat qilish. uning harakatlariga qanday javob berishni tushunish kerak. Shuning uchun biz asosan kurashda yuzaga keladigan uchta turdagi reaksiyalarni ko'rib chiqamiz.

1. Oddiy reaksiya.
2. Murakkab reaksiya.
3. Tanlash reaksiyasi.

Oddiy reaksiya signalga yoki to'satdan signalga o'rganilgan harakat bilan javob berishdir. Misol uchun. Kurashchi texnikaning boshlanishiga tayyorlangan mudofaa yoki qarshi texnika bilan javob beradi. O'rtacha kurashchining oddiy reaksiya vaqti 220-260 m / soniyaga to'g'ri keladi. Bir nechta usullar d) o'zgaruvchan, ya'ni kichik yukdan boshlab, o'rtacha va nihoyat katta yuk bilan tugaydi.

Masalan, o'z vaznidan boshlab, unga og'irlik qo'shib, kuchga yetguncha ko'taring (60-90 kg gacha.) yoki, agar yo'q bo'lsa, aksincha, ya'ni 90 kg dan boshlab katta hajmdan boshlab, 1-2 marta ko'tarilgandan keyin 60 kg vazn mushaklar charchaguncha.

2. Statik mashqlar ba'zi kuchlarga vaqtincha qarshilik ko'rsatadi. Asosan, tinglovchilar ma'lum vaqt davomida shtanga ustida pozitsiyani ushlab turishlari kerak, masalan, burchak holatida turish yoki o'zlaridan og'irroq narsani ko'tarish. Kuchni rivojlantirishda biz asosan og'irliklar bilan bajariladigan mashqlardan foydalanamiz. Bu shtangalar, toshlar, dumbbelllar yoki o'z vazningiz. Tosh bilan bajariladigan mashqlar:

1. Ikki qo'l bilan ko'krigidan toshni ko'tarish.
2. Ikki qo'l bilan boshning orqasida toshni ko'tarish.
3. Tosh bilan o'tirish.
4. Toshni bo'yniga qo'yish. qo'l bilan ushlab turganda tanani burish.
5. Posida turish

Jismoniy mashqlarning tabiati va ularni qo'llash usullariga qarab, tanada uch xil o'zgarishlar bo'lishi mumkin:

1. O'zaro hamkorlik.
2. Neytral.
3. Aksincha, bu bir-biriga xalaqit beradigan vaziyat.

Agar birinchisi mashqlar majmuasida olingan bo'lsa, bu ijobiy ta'sir

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mashqlar. Agar uchinchisi sodir bo'lsa, mashqlarning salbiy ta'siri. Shu munosabat bilan GPTDA jismoniy tarbiya manbalarini to'g'ri tanlashning roli ham muhimdir. "Umumiy jismoniy tarbiya "(GPT). GPTNING asosiy vazifasi tezlik, kuch, chaqqonlik, moslashuvchanlik va chidamlilikni rivojlantirish bo'lishi kerak. GPT yordamida o'zlashtirilgan bu holatlar sport kurashining tabiatini hisobga olgan holda ularning rivojlanishidagi asosiy holatlar hisoblanadi. Yurish, yugurish, suzish, sport o'yinlari, keng qamrovli gimnastika mashqlari GPT manbai hisoblanadi. GPT mashqlarini to'g'ri tanklash kurashchining jismoniy rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shadi. Kurashchi yugurish, sakrash, ko'tarilish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi kerak. mustaqil ravishda yoki boshqa sportchi bilan ishlaydi. Maxsus mashqlarning afzalligi shundaki, ular kurashchiga SPT vazifasini hal qilishda kurash texnikasini o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Tezlashtirish.

Xulosa

Jangchining tezligi-bu qisqa vaqt ichida muayyan harakatlarni bajarish qobiliyati. Agar biz kurashchining tezligi haqida gapiradigan bo'lsak, ideal holda, biz kurashchiga reaksiya berish, raqibni tezda ushlab va texnikani qo'llash yoki mudofaa va qarshi hujum harakatlaridan foydalanish uchun eng kam vaqt sarflashini xohlaymiz. Tezlik xususiyatini ikkita asosiy guruhga bo'lish mumkin. Ulardan biri harakat reaksiyasining turli shakllarining tezligi, ikkinchisi esa harakat tezligining har xil shakli. Harakat reaksiyasining tezligi jang qilish uchun muhimdir. Bunga signal berilgan vaqtdan (ko'rish, eshitish yoki teginish hissi bilan qabul qilingan) javob harakatini boshlashgacha bo'lgan vaqt kiradi.

Oddiy va murakkab harakat reaksiyasi vaqtlari o'zgaradi (0,15 soniyadan 0,5 soniyagacha). Reaksiya tezligi nafaqat himoyada muhim ahamiyatga ega Jismoniy tarbiya umumiy va yordamchi, maxsus tayyorgarlikka bo'linadi: kurashchining umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarligi: u yuqori darajaga chiqish uchun asos va asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Asos quyidagi vazifalarni hal qilishni ta'minlaydi: organizmni jang qilish uchun har tomonlama rivojlantirish, uning funksional imkoniyatlarini oshirish, jismoniy imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish; salomatlikni yaxshilash; intensiv mashg'ulotlar va musobaqa yuklari paytida faol dam olishdan to'g'ri foydalanish.

Aytish mumkinki, harakat reaksiyasining tezligi kurashchining har bir harakatida, harakat mudofaa, qarshi hujum yoki hujum ruhida bo'lishidan qat'i nazar sodir bo'ladi. e'tibor bermaydi, harakat reaksiyalarining tezligi nimaga bog'liq degan savol tug'ilishi mumkin. Ko'rinib turibdiki, kurashchining shaxsiy xususiyatlaridan

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va uning sport formasining holatidan tashqari, uning amaliy tajriba darajasi bilan bog'liqligini ham hisobga olish kerak. Misol uchun, ko'z qochish qiruvchi tushunish bog'liq

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